

THE ELECTRICAL RESPONSE OF STRAINED AND/OR DAMAGED POLYMER MATRIX-COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) consist of the electrically conductive carbon fibre and the polymer matrix, which is an insulator. In glass fibre reinforced composites electrical conductivity can only be achieved if a conductive matrix polymer is used.

The measurement of electrical properties, such as DC-resistivity of continuous CFRP laminates and AC-properties (dielectric properties such as the capacitance and dielectric dissipation), reflects a sensitive possibility for both the recording during tensile, and fatigue testing and the detection of damage, such as fibre fracture, matrix cracks and delamination.

INTRODUCTION

In some literature embedded optical glass fibres were used as sensors for load and fracture in CFRP laminates. In previous publications the authors have shown, that the load carrying carbon fibres themselves can be used to monitor the load response [1,2].

In case of usual metal sample the conductivity is essentially the same for any direction of current flow through the sample. In CFRP samples the conductivity is not homogeneous and depends on the orientation of the fibres. The specific resistivity for carbon fibres ($1500 \times 10^{-8} \Omega\text{m}$) is much higher than that for metals (i.e. aluminium = $2.5 \times 10^{-8} \Omega\text{m}$). The high specific electrical resistivity of the epoxy matrix used is to be seen as an insulator. The current-conducting carbon fibres lead to a certain electrical resistivity of the entire laminate, which mainly depends on the volume fraction and the stacking sequence of the laminate.

Transverse to the fibre direction the electrical resistivity is relatively high. Therefore a CFRP laminate (in thickness direction) reacts as a dielectric material resulting in a certain capacitance and dielectric dissipation when an AC-electric field is applied. These properties depend mainly on the volume fraction and also on the void- and moisture-content of the composite material.

In this publication selected carbon fibres were electrically contacted. It was possible to not only detect load induced damage (fibre fracture or delamination), but also the strain of a CFRP laminate.

The measurement of dielectric properties is already used for the cure monitoring of epoxy resins. In this paper it is shown, that the measurement of the capacitance or dielectric dissipation is highly sensitive to strain of CFRP composites and fibre or matrix cracking.

EXPERIMENTAL

Various laminates with carbon fibre reinforced epoxy matrix systems were used in this investigation. All specimens had a width of 25 mm and a length of 190 mm. The thickness was dependent on the laminate stacking sequence, being about 0.7 mm for the unidirectional laminate $[0]_5$ and 2 mm for the cross-ply laminate $[0_2, 90_2, 0_2, 90_2]_S$ and 2.1 mm for the $[0_2, \pm 45, 0_2, \pm 45, 90]_S$ laminate. End tabs of glass fibre reinforced plastic were used for load transfer and to electrically insulate the specimens from the grips.

DC-EXPERIMENTS

Fig. 1a shows the arrangement used for the measurement of the DC-electrical resistivity. A constant current of about 50 mA was introduced into the end faces of a CFRP test sample. The variation in voltage due to loading could be directly plotted and converted by the simple Ohm's Law into resistivity change. The variation of electrical resistivity with specimen loading was measured on a tensile test machine with a constant crosshead speed of 1 mm/min.

The fatigue tests were performed on a servohydraulic test machine, the specimen temperature being simultaneously measured with a thermocouple. To avoid a heat flux from the test machine into the specimen, the grips were cooled to a constant temperature of about 22°C. Two extensometers were attached to either side of the specimen to provide a continuous measurement of the specimen strain in each load cycle. The variation of the strain rate (in a load controlled test) can be used directly to derive the variation of the secant modulus of the specimen. This can be taken as a damage analogue and is often referred to as "stiffness reduction" [3]. The temperature increase measured due to fatigue loading can also be correlated with damage development [4]. The fatigue tests were performed in tension-tension at a constant R ratio of 0.1 ($R = \text{minimum/maximum stress in a load cycle}$) at a frequency of 10 Hz.

AC-EXPERIMENTS

The electric AC-field was introduced into the specimens via electrodes on adjacent sides, as shown in Fig. 1b. First a round copper film and then a gold film were evaporated on both sides of the specimen surfaces. The copper film adheres to the epoxy matrix because of its possible oxidation. The gold layer serves for minimum electrical resistivity to the also gold covered contacts pressed onto the electrodes via spring forces. This set up allows an easy change of the specimen and a quick zero adjust of the LCR-meter.

Figure 1. a) Schematic illustration of test configuration for monitoring the electrical resistivity, specimen temperature and strain of CFRP specimen b) Introduction of the electric field

The test configuration is schematically shown in Fig. 2. The CFRP specimens were loaded in a tensile testing machine at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. The specimen elongation was measured by strain gauge attached to the specimen. Load and elongation were transferred into stress and strain and recorded versus time. Simultaneously the capacitance and dielectric dissipation of the CFRP specimen between the electrodes were measured by a HP 4284 A Precision LCR-meter at an optimized voltage of 100 mV and frequency of 1 MHz and also recorded versus time.

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of the test configuration for monitoring the capacitance, dielectric dissipation, stress and strain of CFRP specimen

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DC-TESTS

The DC-technique records fibre breakage in form of an increase in electrical resistivity. The observation of fibre fracture within CFRP specimens is in general, not possible during a load test [5], except when fibres split off the specimen surface and can be seen with naked eye, or from acoustic attenuation signals. However, the variation in electrical resistivity during **static loading** is a clear indicator of fibre fracture. Fig. 3 shows the stress/strain curve of a unidirectional specimen together with the variation of electrical resistivity with laminate strain. The electrical resistivity first increases approximately linearly with increasing fibre strain. This increase in resistivity (R) is expected because

$$R = \rho l/A, \quad (1)$$

with ρ : specific electrical resistivity, l : current path length and A : conductor section. The length l increases under tensile load and A decreases. After about 1.25% strain the electrical resistivity no longer varies linearly. The electrical resistivity rises in stepwise fashion to higher values. This can be directly related to increase fibre fracture. The fibre fracture is partly indicated - but with a much lower resolution - in the stress/strain curve.

Figure 3. Tensile test of a unidirectional laminate, showing the stress/strain curve and dependent electrical resistivity variation of a CFRP specimen

The electrical resistivity method, however, cannot only indicate strain and fibre fracture, but also delaminations, one of the most pronounced damage mechanism. In Fig. 4 is shown the result of a tensile test on a unidirectional specimen consisting of 5 plies. The third ply (center ply) was cut through. During initial loading linear elastic deformation occurs, following Hook's law, with a linear increase in electrical resistivity. In the cutted third ply shear stresses transfer the loads from one ply end to the other through the matrix and neighbouring intact plies. When the shear stress exceeds the matrix properties a delamination (under Mode II) initiates, and a plateau is formed in the stress-strain curve. Subsequently the electrical resistivity increases. Only when the delamination growth has come to an end, that is when the third (center)ply is completely separated from the neighbouring plies, a further increase in the stress-strain curve and electrical resistivity can be observed. The reasons are first: During delamination fibres bridging the matrix crack will break and second: An electrical conductivity transverse to the fibre direction is possible at high fibre volume fraction [6]. A delamination will separate touching fibres, this contributes to an increase in electrical resistivity.

Figure 4. Tensile test of a unidirectional laminate. Center ply was cut through. Stress-strain curve and dependent variation of electrical resistivity; both indicating delamination growth.

Figure 5. Tensile test of a quasi-isotropic laminate with edge delamination

This finding can be corroborated when using a quasi-isotropic laminate with $0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ$ and 90° plies. Peel stresses at the specimen edge lead to edge delamination (Fig. 5) demonstrated by the deviation of electrical resistivity from the linear curve.

In Fig. 6 is shown the result of a **fatigue test** on a $[0_2, \pm 45, 0_2, \pm 45, 90]_s$ quasi isotropic laminate. Specimen temperature, electrical resistivity and stiffness reduction (normalized secant modulus) were simultaneously measured and correlated with fatigue life.

Figure 6. Variation of secant modulus, temperature and electrical resistivity during cyclic loading (% of fatigue life), quasi-isotropic laminate

Under fatigue loading, the temperature in a test coupon cannot be regarded as constant; at test frequencies of 10 Hz for example, significant increases in temperature were observed [4]. The variation of the specimen temperature can also be used as a means of detecting damage in a composite. Increasing specimen temperature is a result of increasing (matrix) damage. A good correlation between specimen temperature and stiffness reduction was found in [4].

Fig. 6 suggests the following:

- (1) During the test a continuous increase in temperature, dependent on frequency, maximum load level and fatigue life, can be seen.
- (2) The secant-modulus decreases. The reduction in stiffness can mainly be related to edge delamination growth and the development of transverse cracks in the 90°-ply [5]. However, the stepwise reduction in stiffness has to be related to rupture of the load bearing 0°-fibres.
- (3) The variation in electrical resistivity reflects this situation; with increasing damage (reduction in secant modulus) also the electrical resistivity increases. Due to the stepwise reduction in stiffness also the electrical resistivity responds with a jump in its curve.
- (4) At the initial fatigue loading the electrical resistivity decreases. This is due to the fact, that in carbon fibres the resistivity is temperature dependent and decreases with increasing temperature. Only when the damage growth (delamination, transverse cracks and fibre rupture) accelerates, the electrical resistivity increases again and superposes the temperature dependent resistivity reduction.

AC-TESTS

The observed effect of an increasing load and strain on the capacitance and dielectric dissipation of a CFRP cross-ply laminate (HTA/MY720-LY556) is shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. Tensile test of a cross-ply laminate, showing the stress/strain curve and dependent capacitance and dielectric dissipation (at 1 MHz and 100 mV) of a CFRP specimen

While generally the capacitance decreases, the dissipation increases with increasing load and strain. In Fig. 8 the condition in a CFRP specimen is schematically demonstrated. The high resistivity of the matrix causes a capacitance between the fibres. Close or touching fibres cause current flow between fibres which results in a resistivity. Considering the total specimen thickness between the electrodes we have thus a total capacitance (C_{tot}) and a total resistivity (R_{tot}) [7].

Figure 8. Condition in a CFRP laminate, electrical equivalent circuit and fundamental relations of AC-properties (C: capacitance, R: resistivity (transvers), A: electrode area, d: electrode distance, ϵ_0 : vacuum permittivity, ϵ^* : relative permittivity, ϵ' : dielectric constant, ϵ'' : loss-factor, D: dissipation, X_C : reactance, f: frequency)

From fundamental equation 1 (Fig. 8) one can derive that the capacitance decreases because the dielectric constant (ϵ') of the CFRP material decreases too. A reason for this effect may be that the conductive, load bearing fibres, get closer during loading due to the high poisson ratio of the epoxy matrix. Other parameters such as the vacuum permittivity and the electrode area remain constant during loading. The electrode distance (=specimen thickness) decreases, causing an opposite effect, an increase in capacitance. Also matrix cracks lead to an increase in ϵ' and thus in capacitance due to the formation of new surfaces within the material. These effects may be the reason for the observed unregularities and slope changes in the capacitance curve especially at lower loads where transverse matrix cracks in the 90°-plies occur. From equation 2 (Fig. 8) it can be seen that the dissipation behaves inverse to the capacitance and laminate transverse resistivity. Like the capacitance, the resistivity decreases because the insulating matrix becomes thinner during loading, enabling a current flow between fibres. Thus the dissipation reflects two different physical properties (C and R) which are affected by load and strain with the same tendency.

At about 1% strain of this tensile test fibre breakage occurred in the specimen right between the electrodes. This failure of load bearing fibres leads to a stiffness loss and thus to a drop in load in a displacement controlled test. Locally the former stress of the broken fibres is transferred in neighbouring fibres, resulting in stress concentration and thus in an increasing local stress. Because the fibre breakage was observed to be in the electrode area, the dissipation reacts very sensitive by jumping to a higher level.

CONCLUSIONS

- Measurement of the DC-electrical resistivity, AC-capacitance and dielectric dissipation can be used in situ to detect damage in a carbon/epoxy specimen or component under load.
- Dependent on the load applied to a carbon/epoxy part or specimen, the DC-electrical resistivity, AC-capacitance and dielectric dissipation varies directly as a result of the actual strain or load.
- The conclusion to be drawn is therefore that the measurement of DC-electrical resistivity, AC-capacitance and dielectric dissipation in a CFRP component is a non-destructive evaluation (NDE) technique, with which composite parts can be inspected even when they are in use.
- While the response of the DC-resistivity due to load or strain and fibre breakage is quite well understood, further fundamental investigations will be needed for fully understanding the response of AC-capacitance and dielectric dissipation due to load, strain and different damage mechanisms

REFERENCES

1. K. Schulte, Ch. Baron, Load and failure analysis of cfrp laminates by means of electrical resistivity measurements. *Composites Science and Technology* 36, pp.63-76 (1989).
2. K. Schulte, Damage monitoring in polymer matrix structures. *Journal de Physique IV*, pp. 1629-1636 (1993).
3. R.D. Jamison, K. Schulte, K.L. Reifsnider, W.W. Stinchcomb, Characterization and analysis of damage mechanisms in tension-tension fatigue of graphite/epoxy laminates. *ASTM-STP 836*, Philadelphia, PA, pp. 21-55, (1984)
4. H. Neubert, K. Schulte, H. Harig, Evaluation of the fatigue behaviour by monitoring continuously temperature development in cfrp-laminates. *ASTM-STP 1059*, 435-453 (1990).
5. K. Schulte, W.W. Stinchcomb, Damage mechanisms - including edge effects - in carbon fibre-reinforced composite materials. In: *Application of Fracture Mechanics to Composite Materials*, edited by K. Friedrich, Elsevier Science Publisher, Amsterdam, 273-325 (1989).
6. W.J. Gajda, A fundamental study of the electromagnetic properties of advanced composite materials. *RADC-TR-78-158 AO59029*, (1978).
7. H. Wittich, K. Schulte, M. Kupke, H. Kliem, W. Bauhofer, The Measurement of Electrical Properties of CFRP for Damage Detection and Strain Recording. *Proc. of the ECCM-CTS 2*, pp. 447-458, (1994).